

sensitive variety. They outyielded checks under normal and delayed planting conditions (Table 2). Because of their superior performance in numerous on-farm trials, Satyam and Kishori were released for general

cultivation in rainfed lowlands for normal and delayed monsoon conditions.

Both have intermediate heights (120-125 cm), compact erect habit, and 145-

150-d maturity. Satyam has long fine grains and Kishori has long bold grains. They are resistant to bacterial blight and tolerant of brown spot and Zn and Fe deficiencies. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

On-farm characterization of upland rice varieties in north Thailand

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An on-farm diagnostic survey on the extent and causes of variability of upland rice yields was carried out during 1993-96 in Mae Haeng, Chiang Mai Province, in upper northern Thailand (600-700 masl).

Farmers' varieties were characterized from physiological, agronomic, and genetic points of view. Data were obtained over four successive wet seasons from a total of 423 small squares (1 m²) from 63 farmers' fields representing an extensive range of upland rice-cropping conditions under a predominant swidden cultivation system. Plots were monitored every 2 wk to quantify key physiological and agronomic parameters needed to understand yield buildup patterns of various types of cultivars. Isozyme analysis was carried out to assess the genetic variability of farmers' upland rice varieties.

All upland rice cultivars were found to belong to group 6 (tropical japonicas) of Glaszmann's classification. Heterogeneity was sometimes detected between samples of the same variety coming from different farms. The rare allele 3 at locus *Amp-1* typical of varieties from the Himalayan foothills was observed in some cultivars. Only two late-maturing varieties were found to be glutinous, a type of rice used to

prepare rice cakes during traditional festivals.

Two main types of cultivars, early (95-115 d) and late maturing (138-177 d), were distinguished and played different roles on the farms. Late-maturing varieties clearly constituted the most important type in terms of production volume, whereas early

maturing varieties were planted to improve food security before the main harvesting period. Early and late cultivars were found to be weakly and strongly photoperiod-sensitive, respectively. When expressed in degree days, crop duration cycle was evenly split between the vegetative and reproductive phases for early cultivars

Table 1. Physiological and genetic characteristics of local upland rice varieties in Mae Haeng Village, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, 1993-96.

Variety	Importance	Varietal group ^a	Photoperiodism	Grain type	DD to PI ^b	DD to harvest
<i>Early maturing types</i>						
Chaloina	Rare	Tropical japonica	Weakly sensitive	Nonglutinous	650	1340
Kochokai	Rare				800	1400
Chaloloe	Dominant				670	1350
Kochole	Rare				590	1270
<i>Late maturing types</i>						
Chaae	Rare	Tropical japonica	Strongly sensitive	Nonglutinous	1060	1900
Chanoko	Common			Glutinous	1060	1910
Chafuma	Common			Nonglutinous	1000	1860
Chazu	Rare			Nonglutinous	1230	2120
Komu	Rare			Nonglutinous	1150	1960
Chanona	Rare			Glutinous	860	1790

^aBased on isozyme analysis. ^bDD = degree-days (13 °C threshold temperature), PI = panicle initiation.

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics of Chaloina and Chaae grown in Mae Haeng Village, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand, 1993-96.

Variety	Chaloina	Chaae
Duration	Early	Late
Observations (no.)	75	234
Maximum grain yield (g m ⁻² at 0% H ₂ O)	308	438
Maximum 100-grain weight (g at 0% H ₂ O)	23.2	25.0
Threshold value ^a for filled spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	13,300	17,500
Maximum value for filled spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	16,200	20,600
Maximum grain filling (%)	81	98
Threshold value for spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	20,100	21,500
Maximum value for spikelets m ⁻² (no.)	22,000	26,700
Maximum value for spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	144	183
Threshold value for panicles m ⁻² (no.)	155	146
Maximum value for panicles m ⁻² (no.)	228	237
Maximum value for panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	2.8	3.6
Threshold value for plants m ⁻² (no.)	81	66

^aThreshold value = value required to achieve the maximum for a particular yield component.

whereas for late-maturing ones, the reproductive phase tended to be longer (Table 1).

For the two dominant varieties, Chaloina (early) and Chaae (late), maximum grain yields were measured in fields with no inputs applied but where environmental constraints were minimal. Yields for Chaloina and Chaae reached 308 and 438 g m⁻² at 0% H₂O, respectively (Table 2). These relatively high yields can thus be considered the maximum yield potential in the subsequent analyses of yield buildup processes and agronomic diagnosis of limiting factors and conditions.

Table 2 shows the maximum values of yield components unit area⁻¹ characterizing the classic four successive phases of the yield buildup processes. Threshold values corresponding to the minimum level of the previous yield components required to achieve the potential level of the following one are also provided.

The maximum number of panicles unit area⁻¹ was found to be similar for both varieties but was reached differently. Because of Chaloina's lower maximum number of panicles plant⁻¹, it required a higher threshold of plants m⁻² to achieve a number of panicles (230 m⁻²) similar to the potential achieved by Chaae.

The differentiation in potential yields between Chaloina and Chaae started at spikelet formation and continued in the following phases. A higher maximum number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ was recorded for the late-maturing cultivar as well as a better rate of grain filling (possibly due to more favorable climatic conditions rather than genetic differences) and higher maximum grain weight.

These maxima and the associated threshold values for yield components can be used to construct an empirical model of upland rice yield buildup processes. Such a model can be used for either agronomic diagnoses of limiting factors of yield and for designing and evaluating improved sequences of cultivation practices. ■

Crop resource management

Fertilizer management

Evaluation of P sources in a rice - wheat cropping system in northwestern India

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Increasing costs have resulted in reduced applications of P fertilizers to rice - wheat systems in the Indo-Gangetic plains of India. Partly to address this issue, nitrophosphate P sources have been developed by acidulation of rock phosphate with nitric acid rather than imported and expensive sulfuric acid. These are cheaper than the traditional superphosphate and diammonium phosphate.

We evaluated three nitrophosphate P sources along with superphosphate and diammonium phosphate on wheat (1996-97) and rice (1997) grown in rotation at Ludhiana in northwestern India. The nitrophosphates contained 80% (Narmadaphos), 60% (ammonium nitrophosphate), and 30% (Suphala) of their total P in water-soluble form. Soil

in the experimental field was a Fatehpur loamy sand with 9% clay, 83% sand, 0.33% organic C, pH 7.4, and 11.2 kg P ha⁻¹ (Olsen P). All P sources were applied to wheat at 17.6, 26.4, and 35.2 kg P ha⁻¹ in a randomized complete block design. No P was applied to rice. Nonetheless, the residual effect of the P sources in the following crop of rice was tested. Both wheat and rice were supplied with 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 25 kg K ha⁻¹.

The table shows grain yield and P uptake for both rice and wheat. A significant response of wheat to application of P as superphosphate or diammonium phosphate was observed up to 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹. Nitrophosphate fertilizers possessing 60% and 80% P in water-soluble form were as efficient as wholly water-soluble sources in increasing grain yield and P uptake by wheat. The source with only 30% water-soluble P was significantly inferior to other sources even when applied at higher P levels. No residual effect of any of the five sources was observed on the yield and P uptake of rice. ■

Effect of different applied phosphatic fertilizers on grain yield and P uptake by wheat following a crop of rice. Ludhiana, India, 1996-97.

P source	P level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Wheat		Rice	
		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	P uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	P uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)
No P (control)	0	2.4	7.7	5.2	16.1
Single superphosphate	17.6	3.8	12.3	5.4	17.1
	26.4	4.0	14.1	5.2	16.5
	35.2	4.1	15.9	5.1	15.9
Diammonium phosphate	17.6	4.0	12.9	5.4	16.6
	26.4	4.3	15.1	5.7	17.4
	35.2	4.2	16.0	5.9	17.2
Narmadaphos (80% water-soluble P)	17.6	4.0	13.1	5.2	16.4
	26.4	4.2	15.8	5.6	16.2
	35.2	4.2	15.4	5.8	16.9
Ammonium nitrophosphate (60% water-soluble P)	17.6	4.2	14.2	5.2	16.3
	26.4	4.2	14.8	5.4	15.7
	35.2	4.2	15.4	5.5	16.3
Suphala (30% water-soluble P)	17.6	3.4	12.5	5.0	16.0
	26.4	3.6	13.6	5.7	17.0
	35.2	3.7	13.6	5.2	16.6
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.3	0.7	ns ^a	ns ^a

^ans = not significantly different.